

Higher mobility among researchers identified as potentially talented academics compared to a control group

Aliakbar Akbaritabar*, Robin Haunschild**, and Lutz Bornmann**,**

* akbaritabar@demogr.mpg.de

 0000-0003-3828-1533

Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Rostock, Germany

** R.Haunschild@fkf.mpg.de, L.Bornmann@fkf.mpg.de

 0000-0001-7025-7256

Max Planck Institute for Solid State Research, Stuttgart, Germany

*** bornmann@gv.mpg.de

 0000-0003-0810-7091

Science Policy and Strategy Department

Administrative Headquarters of the Max Planck Society; Munich, Germany

Abstract

In a previous study, identifying potentially talented researchers worldwide using publication data has been proven successful using performance measures compared with citations and funding data. In this study, we investigated scientific mobility among potentially talented researchers and a control group who were also selected based on publication data. We reconstructed the scientific mobility trajectory of these researchers throughout their scientific careers to study whether the potentially talented researchers have a higher propensity to be mobile than the control group. Our results indicate that potentially talented researchers are more likely to be mobile. Higher mobility is a privilege. Specific groups, such as those with fewer caring responsibilities or visa restrictions, could have better access to this privilege. Further research on inequality of access to mobility, and the trade-off between the potential advantages and disadvantages of higher mobility as a strategy to build a successful academic career is necessary.

Keywords: academic talent, bibliometric indicators, scientific mobility

1. Introduction

Research institutions seek methods to identify junior researchers with a potential for higher performance. Since the identification of talented researchers is a time-consuming and complex task that needs knowledge of the respective fields, there is a need for supporting methods. These methods cannot substitute an expert's perspective. They can only support the experts in their decision-making by providing bibliometric information about the applicants' performance or other quantitative information. Although the use of bibliometric information may reduce the costs of the identification of talented individuals, such methods should not be considered as the sole criterion for hiring decisions.

Haunschild and Bornmann (2023) proposed a method and published a dataset including potentially talented individuals to aid selection committees. The method is based on bibliometric data. The essential criterion for being a talented scientist is publication performance at the earlier stages of the career. Haunschild and Bornmann (2023) proposed that potentially talented researchers can be identified by three indicators: (1) the total number of papers, (2) the number of papers in high-impact (Q1) journals, and (3) the number of papers as a corresponding author. Haunschild and Bornmann (2023) tested the validity of their method to identify talented junior researchers using other indicators such as later citation impact and the number of papers linked to grants. Although empirical analyses pointed out that their selection method validly works, it is necessary to undertake further validating research using additional data.

Therefore, this study intends to apply another important indicator for measuring academic success. We are interested in whether researchers who have been identified as potentially talented researchers are more mobile than researchers in a control group. We expect – based on the literature on mobility and academic success (Sugimoto et al., 2017) – that identified talented researchers are more mobile than other researchers.

2. Research on the mobility of researchers: A short overview

With digitalization and the data revolution, bibliometric data is increasingly used as a new source for demographic research (Alburez-Gutierrez et al., 2019; Kashyap et al., 2022). The study of academic mobility has benefited vastly from the availability of large-scale and high-resolution bibliometric data. The literature on scientific mobility roughly focuses on two areas: 1) the experience of mobility and its properties and 2) the by-products and positive or negative impacts of mobility.

The first group of literature considers the geographic scale of academic mobility (national versus international mobility). Some look at internal (i.e., sub-national moves inside a country) or international migration to/from a country – see the cases of Russia (Subbotin & Aref, 2021), Mexico (Miranda-González et al., 2020), and Germany (X. Zhao et al., 2021). Others have focused on the global mobility of scholars (Akbaritabar et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2023; Sanliturk et al., 2023; Robinson-Garcia et al., 2019).

The second group of literature looks at (dis)advantages or insignificances (Aksnes et al., 2013) of mobility, or its contributions to the scientific field, knowledge transfer, institutional, national or global productivity, and innovation. Some research has focused on the performance and impact of mobile scientists or the so-called “mover’s advantage” (Franzoni et al., 2014). Other research has looked at these scholars’ contributions to specific fields or national contexts and knowledge transfer (Aman, 2020). A few studies have focused on the disadvantages of scientific mobility, such as instability in collaborations (Zhao et al., 2020) and unequal access to scientific mobility due to care (children and elderly care) or other familial responsibilities (Schaer et al. 2017).

One reason for the frequently found better performance of mobile researchers might be stimulating departmental effects on researchers traveling to favourable environments. Many past studies have shown that the performance of researchers is influenced by the institutional environment: Researchers increase their performance when they work with a group of productive colleagues (Bonaccorsi, Belingheri, & Secondi, 2021). This influence is proposed to be even stronger when star scientists or very productive researchers are part of the environment (Li, Aste, Caccioli, & Livan, 2019), and the environment is located in prestigious departments or universities (Amara, Landry, & Halilem, 2015; Way, Morgan, Larremore, & Clauset, 2019). The influence of the environment will not only be of a motivational nature, but also be manifested in co-publishing papers. The results by Li, Yin, Fortunato, & Wang (2020) show that very successful researchers, i.e., Nobel laureates, have a greater propensity towards collaborations in their early careers than a comparison group. The importance of collaboration and interaction for successful scientific careers has also been confirmed by Zalewska-Kurek, Geurts, & Roosendaal (2010).

Another reason for the frequently better performance of mobile researchers (besides the stimulating environment that influences researchers and makes them better) is the individual academic ability to do research: The more productive researchers are positively selected

(Sugimoto et al., 2017; Franzoni et al., 2014) to be hired in higher-performing countries and institutions as they try to attract “the best and the brightest” (Kapur & McHale, 2005).

3. Materials and Methods

To identify authors’ mobility, we used all articles and reviews (more than 28 million) published by more than 8 million authors as indexed in a 2020 snapshot of Elsevier’s Scopus database (Baas et al, 2020). These 8 million authors are a subset of all Scopus authors who have a higher quality of name disambiguation than the rest of the Scopus authors. The data is prepared as an in-house database and access to it is provided to us by the Kompetenznetzwerk Bibliometrie (KB, 2021). We used this data to identify (1) potentially talented researchers (i.e., the observation group in this study) and a control group based on bibliometric measures proposed by Haunschild and Bornmann (2023), and (2) mobility events throughout the researcher’s publishing career:

(1) Haunschild and Bornmann (2023) applied three indicators in various combinations to identify potentially talented researchers: number of publications in top-quartile journals (Q1), number of all publications (O), and number of publications where the focal author is the corresponding author (C). Following Haunschild and Bornmann (2023), we separated the authors for this study, who published their first paper indexed in Scopus between 1999 and 2003, into two groups: (I) Authors belonging to the top-1% within a broad field (two-digit All Science Journal Classification, ASJC, scheme) are defined as the group of potentially talented individuals, i.e., the observation group. (II) Authors belonging to the group between the top-10% and the top-5% within a broad field (two-digit ASJC) are defined as the control group. Since authors may publish research in different fields, some authors might be in the control group in one field and in the group of potentially talented individuals in another field. In our statistical analysis described below, we deduplicated the data and used distinct authors per group. Some ASJCs (multidisciplinary, social sciences, and humanities) were excluded from the analysis. Papers published in journals from multidisciplinary fields cannot be assigned to a specific field using the ASJC scheme, and the use of bibliometrics in social sciences and humanities is critically seen (Haunschild and Bornmann, 2023).

(2) We identified mobility events of authors by tracking a change in academic affiliation addresses in the publications (Akbaritabar et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2023). For instance, once an author who had previously published with an affiliation in the United States publishes a new article with an affiliation in Germany, we can use this as a signal for a mobility event. To reduce noise in the data due to shorter-term mobility, we used a “mode-based” method. This method considers multiple affiliations that one holds in one publication and/or in different publications in a given year and reduces them to the most frequently occurring affiliation address, i.e., the mode, as the probable country of residence for that year. In the next step, we checked if this mode affiliation address had changed compared to the previous year and the next. This approach limited the mobility events to those lasting at least one year.

The different combinations of Q1, O, and C resulted in different numbers of potentially talented researchers and authors in the control group. Haunschild and Bornmann (2023) identified the best performing combination of indicators (Q1, O, and C) in terms of being most distant to the control group. They recommend focusing on this combination in the search for possible talented

individuals. We followed their recommendation and used the “OxQ1” indicator combination in our statistical analysis. Table 1 shows the OxQ1 combination of bibliometric indicators and the number of authors (third column) and after joining with mobility data identified using Scopus (fourth column). As the results in the table show, the joining reduces the counts. This reduction results from using a conservative approach to identify mobility events based on mode-affiliation (described above). In pre-processing, we excluded authors who have only one publication in the database. By definition, they cannot experience mobility.

Table 1. Number of authors for each group and indicator combination.

Group	Indicator combination	Number of authors before adding mobility status	Number of authors after adding mobility status
Observation group	OxQ1	15,188	14,825
Control group	OxQ1	14,904	14,223
Differences between the observation group and control group	OxQ1	284	602

For the validation of the methods for identifying potentially talented researchers and to study their relation with scientific mobility, we investigated whether potentially talented individuals are more mobile than the researchers in the control group. Academic success is usually linked to greater mobility (see the background section). Our outcome variable is thus the mobility status which is categorical including categories such as (1) researchers who have not been mobile at all in their academic career (i.e., the category indicated as “non-mobile” in the results section), (2) researchers who have experienced mobility inside one country and have not moved abroad (category “mobile internal”), (3) researchers who have been mobile between at least two distinct countries (category “mobile international”), and (4) researchers who have experienced both internal and international mobility in their career (category “mobile both”).

We modelled the probability of a scholar being in each of the mobility categories based on the independent variable, i.e., membership in the group of potentially talented individuals or the control group. Since this outcome variable is categorical with more than two categories, we used both multinomial logistic and probit models. The latter has less restricted assumptions, such as the independence of irrelevant alternatives (IIA). Although this better treatment of assumptions comes at the cost of being computationally more expensive, we checked if our results are robust to the choice of different models. Since the results were similar between multinomial logit and probit models, we used the family of multinomial probit models.

4. Results

Figure 1 provides a descriptive summary of the differences between control and observation group members in mobility status: Potentially talented individuals have a higher representation among those who are mobile internally, internationally, or both. Potentially talented individuals (observation group) have a lower representation among non-mobile authors (red dots and solid line).

Figure 1. Descriptive percentage of unique authors (y axis) in control and observation groups (x axis) grouped by mobility status (line colour/type).

Table 2 shows the coefficients of the multinomial probit regression model with mobility status as the dependent variable – with three categories (internal, international, and both) – and membership in control and observation groups as the independent variable.

Table 2. Coefficients of the multinomial probit regression model with mobility status as the dependent variable with three categories (internal, international, and both), and membership in control and observation groups as the independent variable.

	<i>Categories of dependent variable: mobility</i>		
	Both	Internal	International
Observation group	0.295*** (0.042)	0.119*** (0.030)	0.158*** (0.032)
Reference category (control group)	-1.674*** (0.032)	-0.618*** (0.021)	-0.824*** (0.023)
Akaike information criterion (AIC)	71666.17		
Bayesian information criterion (BIC)	71715.69		
Log Likelihood	-35827.08		
Number of observations	28406		

Notes: Significance levels:
* p<0.1; ** p<0.05; *** p<0.01

To simplify the interpretation of the results from the regression analysis, Figure 2 shows the predicted probabilities of the statistical model. The results in the figure reveal that potentially talented researchers have a higher predicted probability of being mobile in all three categories and a lower predicted probability of being non-mobile.

Figure 2. Predicted probability of mobility and being non-mobile between control and observation groups.

5. Discussion

This study is a follow-up study to research by Haunschild and Bornmann (2023). The authors developed a bibliometric method for identifying potentially talented individuals. Bibliometric information cannot be the sole criterion for hiring decisions, but it can support expert decision on potentially talented researchers. Haunschild and Bornmann (2023) tested the validity of the methods based on citation impact and grant data linked to publications published later in careers. Although the results based on citation and grant data could confirm the developed method, it is necessary to investigate the method in further studies. In this study, therefore, we used data on the mobility of researchers to validate the method using criteria other than citation and grant data. Successful careers are usually linked to academic mobility, and this link is independently set from the field one is interested in.

In recent years, several studies on the mobility of researchers have been published based on comprehensive bibliometric databases. In this study, we also analyzed mobility in detail by using data from a comprehensive database: Which authors have a higher or a lower propensity to be mobile inside the same country (internal mobility) and between multiple countries (international mobility)? Which authors have experienced both types of mobility compared to

non-mobile authors? We constructed a sample of authors grouped into control and observation groups following the requirements of Haunschild and Bornmann (2023).

The results of our study reveal that potentially talented individuals (authors with high performance in bibliometric indicators) show a higher propensity than the control group to be mobile in all types of mobility investigated here. Potentially talented researchers not only receive more citation impact for their papers and more grants in their careers (as the previous study indicated), they are also more mobile. The greater mobility of the potentially talented researchers could be driven by the fact that these authors have been more productive and published a higher number of papers earlier in their careers; that might be why they were more attractive for other institutions than other researchers. However, it could also be vice versa: Higher mobility (in the early career) could be the reason for a higher publication output in general and a higher output in top-quartile journals not only in the early, but also in the late phases of the career. Higher mobility may be a privilege in the early career. Specific groups, such as those with fewer caring responsibilities or visa restrictions, could have better access to this privilege (Derrick et al, 2022; Zhao et al, 2023).

Further research on the trade-off between the potential advantages and disadvantages of higher mobility for a successful academic career and unequal access to mobility is necessary. We recommend that this research considers the limitations of our study. Scopus is dominated by English publications, mainly from the Global North countries and hard sciences. This can, in principle, (i) overrepresent certain groups among the authors we identified as potentially talented researchers and mobile and (ii) underrepresent the scientific production of authors from the Global South, non-English language countries, and non-Western countries. Another limitation concerns the interpretation of the empirical results. The results of this study point to a correlation between being a potential talent or not (in terms of bibliometric performance) and mobility. Since the causality of the correlation cannot be completely solved, follow-up studies may use improved study designs (e.g., by considering the temporal sequence of single mobility events and the later publication performance and vice versa). Despite these limitations, our results shed light on different propensities and positive selection of the potentially talented authors towards higher mobility compared to authors from the control group.

Open science practices

We used Scopus data to study scientific mobility among potentially talented scholars and compared them with a control group. We constructed a scholar's publication and mobility trajectory using bibliometric data. This required identifying the scholar and differentiating them from other scholars with similar names, i.e., homonyms. Since author name disambiguation is crucial for our analysis, we used Scopus' proprietary data. There are open-access alternative databases, such as OpenAlex, that could, in principle, be used for this research. The problem with OpenAlex is that the quality of author disambiguation has not been evaluated yet.

Author contributions

AA: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization

RH: Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing

LB: Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Methodology

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding information

We have received access to the bibliometric data through the project “Kompetenznetzwerk Bibliometrie (KB, 2021)” (see <https://bibliometrie.info/en/>), and we acknowledge their funder Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (grant number 16WIK2101A).

References

- Akbaritabar, A., Theile, T., & Zagheni, E. (2024). Bilateral flows and rates of international migration of scholars for 210 countries for the period 1998-2020. *Scientific Data*, *11*(1), 816. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03655-9>
- Aksnes, D. W., Rørstad, K., Piro, F. N., & Sivertsen, G. (2013). Are mobile researchers more productive and cited than non-mobile researchers? A large-scale study of Norwegian scientists. *Research Evaluation*, *22*(4), 215–223. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvt012>.
- Alburez-Gutierrez, D., Zagheni, E., Aref, S., Gil-Clavel, S., Grow, A., & Negraia, D. V. (2019). *Demography in the digital era: New data sources for population research*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/24jp7>.
- Aman, V. (2020). Transfer of knowledge through international scientific mobility: Introduction of a network-based bibliometric approach to study different knowledge types. *Quantitative Science Studies*, *1*(2), 565-581. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00028.
- Amara, N., Landry, R., & Halilem, N. (2015). What can university administrators do to increase the publication and citation scores of their faculty members? *Scientometrics*, *103*(2), 489-530. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-015-1537-2>.
- Baas, J., Schotten, M., Plume, A., Côté, G., & Karimi, R. (2020). Scopus as a curated, high-quality bibliometric data source for academic research in quantitative science studies. *Quantitative Science Studies*, *1*(1), 377–386. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00019.
- Bonaccorsi, A., Belingheri, P., & Secondi, L. (2021). The research productivity of universities. A multilevel and multidisciplinary analysis on European institutions. *Journal of Informetrics*, *15*(2), 101129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2020.101129>.
- Derrick, G. E., Chen, P.-Y., van Leeuwen, T., Larivière, V., & Sugimoto, C. R. (2022). The relationship between parenting engagement and academic performance. *Scientific Reports*, *12*(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-26258-z>
- Franzoni, C., Scellato, G., & Stephan, P. (2014). The mover’s advantage: The superior performance of migrant scientists. *Economics Letters*, *122*(1), 89–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econlet.2013.10.040>.
- German Competence Network for Bibliometrics. (2021). *Kompetenznetzwerk Bibliometrie (KB)*. <https://bibliometrie.info/>, accessed on November 02, 2021.
- Haunschild, R., & Bornmann, L. (2023). Identification of potential young talented individuals in the natural and life sciences: A bibliometric approach. *Journal of Informetrics*, *17*(3), 101394. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2023.101394>.

Kapur, D., & McHale, J. (2005). *Give us your best and brightest: The global hunt for talent and its impact on the developing world*. Center for Global Development.
<https://www.cgdev.org/sites/default/files/9781933286037-Kapur-Hale-best-and-brightest.pdf>, accessed on April 06, 2021.

Kashyap, R., Rinderknecht, R. G., Akbaritabar, A., Alburez-Gutierrez, D., Gil-Clavel, S., Grow, A., Kim, J., Leasure, D. R., Lohmann, S., Negraia, D. V., Perrotta, D., Rampazzo, F., Tsai, C.-J., Verhagen, M. D., Zagheni, E., & Zhao, X. (2023). *Digital and computational demography*. In *Research Handbook on Digital Sociology* (pp. 48–86). Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://www.elgaronline.com/edcollchap/book/9781789906769/book-part-9781789906769-10.xml>.

Li, J., Yin, Y., Fortunato, S., & Wang, D. (2020). Scientific elite revisited: Patterns of productivity, collaboration, authorship and impact. *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*, 17(165), 20200135. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsif.2020.0135>.

Li, W. H., Aste, T., Caccioli, F., & Livan, G. (2019). Early coauthorship with top scientists predicts success in academic careers. *Nature Communications*, 10(5170).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-13130-4>.

Miranda-González, A., Aref, S., Theile, T., & Zagheni, E. (2020). Scholarly migration within Mexico: Analyzing internal migration among researchers using Scopus longitudinal bibliometric data. *EPJ Data Science*, 9(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjds/s13688-020-00252-9>.

Robinson-Garcia, N., Sugimoto, C. R., Murray, D., Yegros-Yegros, A., Larivière, V., & Costas, R. (2019). The many faces of mobility: Using bibliometric data to measure the movement of scientists. *Journal of Informetrics*, 13(1), 50–63.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2018.11.002>.

Sanliturk, E., Zagheni, E., Daňko, M. J., Theile, T., & Akbaritabar, A. (2023). Global patterns of migration of scholars with economic development. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 120(4), e2217937120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2217937120>.

Schaer, M., Dahinden, J., & Toader, A. (2017). Transnational mobility among early-career academics: Gendered aspects of negotiations and arrangements within heterosexual couples. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 43(8), 1292–1307.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2017.1300254>.

Subbotin, A., & Aref, S. (2021). Brain drain and brain gain in Russia: Analyzing international migration of researchers by discipline using Scopus bibliometric data 1996–2020. *Scientometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-04091-x>.

Sugimoto, C. R., Robinson-Garcia, N., Murray, D. S., Yegros-Yegros, A., Costas, R., & Larivière, V. (2017). Scientists have most impact when they're free to move. *Nature*, 550(7674), 29–31. <https://doi.org/10.1038/550029a>.

Way, S. F., Morgan, A. C., Larremore, D. B., & Clauset, A. (2019). Productivity, prominence, and the effects of academic environment. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116(22), 10729–10733. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1817431116>.

Zalewska-Kurek, K., Geurts, P. A. T. M., & Roosendaal, H. E. (2010). The impact of the autonomy and interdependence of individual researchers on their production of knowledge and its impact: an empirical study of a nanotechnology institute. *Research Evaluation*, 19(3), 217-225. <https://doi.org/10.3152/095820210x503474>.

Zhao, X., Akbaritabar, A., Kashyap, R., & Zagheni, E. (2023). A gender perspective on the global migration of scholars. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 120(10), e2214664120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2214664120>.

Zhao, X., Aref, S., Zagheni, E., & Stecklov, G. (2022). Return migration of German-affiliated researchers: Analyzing departure and return by gender, cohort, and discipline using Scopus bibliometric data 1996–2020. *Scientometrics*, 127, 7707-7729, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04351-4>.

Zhao, Z., Bu, Y., & Li, J. (2020). Does the mobility of scientists disrupt their collaboration stability? *Journal of Information Science*, 48(2), 016555152094874. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551520948744>.